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**EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area**

Deliverable No. 7.4

**Implementation of the Advisory Board (AB) incl.
terms of reference**

Submission of Deliverable

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

From 2020-2024, EU-PolarNet 2 will provide a platform to further develop the coordination of Polar research actions in Europe and with overseas partners. At the beginning of the project, EU-PolarNet 2 will set up all its support panels, amongst them the Advisory Board (AB). This board is comprised of roughly eight persons, including respected international representatives of Polar-related research organisations, representatives from European Indigenous organisations and local/regional authorities, and stakeholders from industry, NGOs and politics.

The role of the Advisory Board is to assist in reviewing the project's developments and progress, to support strategic decisions and wherever possible contribute to EU-PolarNet 2's success in developing a European Polar Research Area.

Introduction

EU-PolarNet 2 is the continuation of EU-PolarNet, which has been a central plank of the European Union's Polar research efforts as the integrated EU policy for the Arctic states. The consortium consists of 25 partners representing all European Member States and Associated Countries that have well-established Polar Programmes. The main objective of this four-year project is to establish a sustainable and inclusive platform to co-develop and advance European Polar research actions and to give evidence-based advice to policymaking processes. By involving all relevant stake- and rightholders, EU-PolarNet 2 will support the development of transdisciplinary and transnational Polar research actions of high societal relevance. EU-PolarNet 2 will operate as this platform during its lifetime and will endeavour to sustain the platform in a European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO) after EU-PolarNet 2 ends as a key building block to establish a European Polar Research Area.

To achieve this aim, EU-PolarNet 2 sets up an Advisory Board (AB), whose role will be to assist in reviewing the project's developments and progress, and wherever possible to contribute to EU-PolarNet 2's success in developing a European Polar Research Area.

In accepting membership of the EU-PolarNet 2 Advisory Board (AB), the individual member agrees to be bound by the Terms of Reference (ToR) enclosed.

EU-POLARNET 2 ADVISORY BOARD TERMS OF REFERENCE

1. General context

EU-PolarNet 2 – coordinating and co-designing the European Polar research area - was launched on the first of October 2020, bringing together 25 partners from all 21 European and Associated Countries with substantial Polar activities.

The ambition of EU-PolarNet 2 is to establish a sustainable and inclusive platform to co-develop and advance European Polar research actions and to give evidence-based advice to policymaking processes. The overall objective of the project is to support and strengthen the coordination and cooperation in European Polar research. To achieve this, EU-PolarNet 2 has six specific objectives with measurable outcomes:

- (1) Research Coordination - Advancing European and International Polar research coordination
- (2) Stakeholder Involvement - Providing strategies for capacity building related to meaningful stakeholder involvement
- (3) Research Prioritisation - Advancing European Polar research strategies and supporting the development of large-scale international Polar initiatives
- (4) Research Optimisation - Interaction with national funding agencies to build synergies and optimise the use of resources
- (5) Policy Advice, Dissemination, Communication - Providing evidence-based policy advice
- (6) European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO) - Supporting the implementation of sustained observation systems in the Arctic and Antarctic by setting up a European Polar Coordination Office (WP6)

Once EU-PolarNet 2 ends, the gained experience, the established network and the tools developed to facilitate better coordination and co-design of Polar research actions will be transferred to and sustained by the European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO).

The success of EU-PolarNet 2 will be measured by the following, expected impacts:

- 1) Support of the creation of a European Polar Research Area and a substantially advanced Polar research cooperation in Europe.
- 2) Contribution to improved coordination of national resources and investments in European Polar research to ensure their more synergetic use.
- 3) Improved policy advice at regional, national and EU level and support of the EU's international commitments with respect to Polar sciences.
- 4) Improved cooperation of international Polar research programmes to create the basis for the development of future large-scale joint international Polar initiatives.
- 5) European-wide agreed and prioritised Polar research actions.

2. Objectives of the Advisory Board

The purpose of the Advisory Board is to provide recommendations and support to the strategic steering of EU-PolarNet 2, in close cooperation with the General Assembly and Executive Board.

The roles of the Advisory Board are:

- to accompany and support the progress of the project
- to advise the project in all questions related to achieving the above-mentioned objectives,
- to stimulate connections with stake- and rightholders, international partners and organisations as well as with other European initiatives and projects.
- to ensure the transparency of the decision process for applications to the calls for services
- to avoid any potential conflicts of interest within the project, and advise the Management Support Team in any disputes that may occur.

The Advisory Board will fulfill this role by:

- being composed of recognized experts and representatives of the key sectors and actors of the Polar Regions;
- being invited to attend EU-PolarNet 2 meetings on request;
- participating in the EU-PolarNet 2 General Assembly meetings;
- acting as a peer review panel of the project results.

In operational terms, the Advisory Board will:

- communicate directly with the Project coordinator and Management Support Team. The Project coordinator and Management Support Team will report to the Executive Board and record it in the minutes from the Executive Board meetings.
- provide advice and share their own experience in response to issues put across by the Management Support Team
- pro-actively propose own topics for discussion if relevant
- advice on the following issues:
 - project progress through selected highlights such as white papers
 - calls for services: focus areas, development of the award concept and lessons learnt during the award process
 - sustainability of the project achievements beyond the project's life-span
 - involvement of different stakeholder groups
- seek advice from external experts, if considered beneficial
- only have an advisory role, and no voting rights in any project related issues

3. Membership

3.1. Composition

The Advisory Board consists of around eight international recognised experts, which shall have diverse experiences and represent the following: Polar-related research organisations, European Indigenous organisations and local/regional authorities, stakeholders from industry, NGOs and politics. Should it turn out during the project that an expertise is missing in the Advisory Board, additional members can be nominated. All members of the Advisory Board serve as volunteers.

EU-PolarNet 2 will aim for a balanced gender composition of the Advisory Board.

3.2. Nomination and membership criteria

The members of the Advisory Board are nominated by the EU-PolarNet 2 Executive Board and invited by the Management Support Team on behalf of the Consortium. The nominee must meet the following minimum criteria:

- representation of different Polar organizations, institutions or sectors listed in the composition criteria;
- a high personal and professional integrity;
- a sound judgement, derived from experience in management or policy-making, scientific research or other qualifications and experiences, which allow them to function in an advisory role;
- demonstration of, through previous involvements in committees, panels or projects, the willingness to devote adequate effort to the Advisory Board responsibilities.

In the event that a Panel member no longer meets the requirements then his/her membership shall cease, and the vacancy shall be filled.

3.3. Current membership

The members of the Panel are listed in **Appendix 1** hereto. The membership is terminated automatically with the end of the EU-PolarNet 2 project.

3.4. Membership acknowledgement

The Membership in the Advisory Board is voluntary and unremunerated. The composition and membership in the Advisory Board will be publicly acknowledged on the EU-PolarNet 2 website, www.eu-polarnet.eu, unless an AB member explicitly asks for her/his membership to AB to remain confidential.

3.5. Chair & co-chair

The chair (and co-chair) of the AB will be elected from the board members and recommended to the GA for approval.

Duties

- The chair(s) will oversee an efficient and effective operation of the Advisory Board in accordance with the Terms of Reference.
- In fulfilling these duties, the chair(s) will use best endeavors to act independently in accordance with any legal or regulatory requirements.

Appointment

- The chair(s) will be elected by a simple majority vote of the Advisory Board members and finally endorsed by the Executive Board.
- Any person appointed for membership of the Advisory Board must be prepared to serve as chair if selected.

Termination

- The term of office of the chair(s) is two years, with the possibility of re-election for one more term.
- By notice served by the EU-PolarNet 2 coordinator and endorsed by the Executive Board, the chair/co-chair may be removed from office if he/she
 - ceases to fulfil the requirements of membership of the Advisory Board,
 - becomes incapable of performing the functions of the office as outlined in the Terms of Reference whether by illness, infirmity, or incompetence,
 - or is found by a properly constituted supervisory authority to have breached any law or regulation applicable to his/her professional role.

4. Duties and limits of the Advisory Board

The Advisory Board will provide independent advice to the General Assembly, Executive Board and Project Coordinator on the issues outlined in the ToR. Advisory Board recommendations are not binding for the consortium that may accept, amend or reject them.

The Advisory Board is asked to critically review the project progress (e.g. deliverables, milestones) to ensure their relevance and excellence and to provide important feedback to the EU-PolarNet 2 Consortium.

AB members are expected to participate once a year in the General Assembly (face-to-face, if possible) and in a few virtual meetings on request or e-mail exchanges in-between when consulted on the issues they should advice on, as stated in the ToR.

Members of the Advisory Board will have no voting rights at any EU-PolarNet 2 meetings or decisions.

Confidentiality: The Advisory Board has the duty to protect all confidential and non-public information, such as draft versions of project deliverables, outcomes of calls for services or discussions within the Advisory Board. The members of the Advisory Board accept this confidentiality clause with the written consent (e-mail) of the ToR.

5. Meetings

The Advisory Board will meet at least once per year and when it is deemed necessary, on request of the Project Coordinator. The Management Support Team will be responsible for the convening of meetings, preparation and circulation of minutes, reporting and timely follow-up of agreed actions. Furthermore, Advisory Board Members will be invited to attend EU-PolarNet 2 meetings of interest and they should participate in the yearly General Assembly meetings, to provide critical assessment

of the quality of the project by acting as a peer review panel with respect to the results, as well as the networking and outreach activities.

The conduct of meetings via modern support such as email exchanges or video-/tele-conferencing is strongly encouraged.

In case of an in-person meeting, Advisory Board Members will be reimbursed by the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium for their travel/accommodation costs in line with the project budget rules.

Appendix

Table: Confirmed members of the EU-PolarNet 2 Advisory Board, as of March 2021.

Background	Surname	First Name	Role/Institution
Indigenous representative	Omma	Elle Merete	Head of EU Unit of the Saami Council
Regional government	Rännäli-Kontturi	Anne	International Affairs Manager at the city of Oulu and members of the Arctic Mayors Forum
Industry representative / cruise tourism	Dubreuil*	Nicolas	Managing Partner at SEDNA; Formerly Ponant
NGO	Christian	Claire	Executive director of ASOC
Policy/Decision maker	Villegas	Marina	Spanish Research Council (CSIC) delegate for Madrid regional affairs, former director of the Spanish Polar Committee
Scientific Organisations	Meloni	Antonio	SCAR
Scientific Organisations	Fugmann	Gerlis	Executive Secretary of IASC
EU Polar Cluster	Grist	Hannah	Work Package Leader in Blue Action (EU Polar Cluster) and communication specialist

*Chair of the AB.